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STUDYING THE CONNECTION BETWEEN QUASIHARMONIC COMPONENTS
OF A SPEECH SIGNAL

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A harmonic model in the form of superposition of oscillations with a fundamental frequency and overtones is widely applied in the speech signal processing. It is of interest to study not only components of the harmonic model but also their possible interconnections. The revelation of such interconnections and their further detail could appear to be usable for solving the problems of speech sound recognition and speaker identification. This article demonstrates the efficiency of the speech signal bispectral analysis. The data of digital bispectral processing of the voiced speech sounds using both speech signal and its parametric description provided by the linear prediction model have been figured out.

Introduction. Analysis of phase couplings between harmonic or quasi-harmonic oscillations having multiple frequencies and the frequencies in rational relations has been widely and successfully applied for many kinds of super-broadband and polyharmonic signals [1-3]. The most spectacular example of this analysis is evaluation of the current phase differences for quasi-harmonic oscillations observed at the base frequency, as well as the overtones of a speech signal [3]. These evaluations appear to be negligibly changing with the duration of pure sounds, being different for various sounds, and individual and stable for various speakers [2, 3]. Information contained in them can be used for speech sound recognition and speaker identification purposes.

Recently bispectral processing methods have enjoyed extensive use for revealing coherence of quasi-harmonic oscillations in frequency and phase [4-6]. These methods make it possible to obtain new informative attributes and offer signal recognition solutions in many spheres. This paper studies the application of such methods in speech technologies.

Estimates of the speech signal bispectrum. Instability of the vocalized speech signal parameters presents a major complexity in evaluation of the component-to-component phase couplings. In terms of the speech signal parametric models, variations in the spectral envelope (formant structure) and pitch create a considerable difficulty. In order to prevent variations in characteristics from affecting the assessments, obtained in the course of the bispectral analysis, it seems reasonable to use parametric description of the speech signal. For this it appears feasible to divide the signal into the excitation sequence that characterizes the pitch, and the spectral envelope. In this paper linear prediction is employed as a tool for such division. Search for potential phase couplings was performed by bispectral analysis of the initial speech signal, the excitation signal, and frequency response of the inverted predictor filter. Evaluation of the predictor filter is of a certain concern, since it defines the shape of the spectral envelope and shows little dependence on changes in the pitch frequency.

Bispectral estimates were made in the frequency domain by a direct method [4], based on the use of the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). This method is deemed convenient to work with signals in time and frequency domains, and can be easily adjusted to calculate bispectral estimates based on the linear prediction model. The procedure of the bispectral estimate consists of four basic steps, enumerated below.

Step 1: the signal is divided into K segments having N samples each, then an average value is deducted out of each segment;

Step 2: DFT coefficients are calculated for each segment $\{x^{(k)}(n)\}$:

$$X^{(k)}(m) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x^{(k)}(n) \exp\left(\frac{-j2\pi mn}{N}\right), \quad (1)$$

where $k = \overline{1, K}$, $n = \overline{0, N-1}$, and $m = \overline{0, N/2}$.

Step 3: A short-time bispectrum is calculated

$$\hat{b}^{(k)}(f_1, f_2) = X(f_1)X(f_2)X^*(f_1 + f_2) \quad (2)$$

Within a triangular area $f_1 = \overline{0, N/2}$, $f_2 = \overline{0, f_1}$, $f_1 + f_2 \leq N/2$.

Step 4: The bispectrum estimate with the available data is equal to the average value for K segments:

$$\hat{B}(f_1, f_2) = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \hat{b}^{(k)}(f_1, f_2). \quad (3)$$

It is well-known that the linear prediction model generated the excitation signal, close in shape to that of a sequence of unit impulses, by virtue of straightening of the spectral envelope of the initial signal and changing the phase values of its spectral components. The linear prediction model has been modified in order to obtain the phase pattern of the initial signal. The predictor filter $A(z)$ was estimated with the aid of the conventional autocorrelation method. Further a high-order filter was synthesized with a linear phase response, corresponding to the frequency-gain response of the predictor filter obtained. The synthesis procedure consists in the following:

- calculate the predictor filter factor $a_{1,k}$ (k -is the predictor order) using the autocorrelation method;
- add zeros to the sequence of factors $a_{1,k}$ and calculate the amplitude spectrum using the Fourier Transform;
- derive the inverse Fourier Transform from the amplitude spectrum obtained, and rearrange the right and left parts of the resulting sequence.

In order to obtain the bispectrum of the frequency response for the inverted predictor filter (synthesis filter) the value of the expression $1/A(e^{j\lambda})$ for $\lambda \in [0, \pi]$ was calculated in place of the Fourier Transform (step 2 of the bispectrum algorithm).

The described ways allow calculating the speech signal bispectrum and its parametric components (the excitation signal and speech response of the voice tract)

Experimental results. A specific analysis tool has been created in the MATLAB environment to estimate the bispectrum (the internet address: <http://bispectrum.googlecode.com/svn/trunk/bispectrum>). The flow diagrams of the program and analysis algorithm are presented in Fig. 1 and 2, respectively. Designations, used in the flow diagrams, correspond to those used in the indicated program code. Finding correspondence between those designations and symbols in formulas (1-3) does not present any problems. The program enables to process sound files in the .wav format. There is a vocal base containing speech samples of four speakers prepared. The speech was recorded at a sampling rate of 16 kHz. The base includes speech signals of four types, namely: natural speech, prolonged vowel with fixed pitch, and prolonged vowel with pitch modulations. This provided for a possibility to compare the bispectrum of the intermittent speech signal was and a speech signal with fixed parameters of the speech production. Bispectrum of the initial signal, excitation signal, and frequency response of the synthesis filter were calculated in order to record the speech signal of each type. The analysis was performed by frames of 0.1 s at an analysis step of 0.05s, FFT format – 1024 samples. Fig. 3 illustrates an example of the bispectrum analysis of the excitation signal and spectral envelope of the vowel ‘Λ’ (bispectrum is given in dB). The general results of the phase coupling estimate are reviewed in Table 1.

Table 1. Component-to-component phase coupling

	Original signal	Excitation signal	Synthesis filter
Continued natural speech	No observable coupling	No observable coupling	No observable coupling
A vowel with fixed pitch frequency	Several first harmonics are coupled	All the harmonics of the vocalized area in the spectrum are coupled	Areas of the second and third formants are coupled with the entire spectrum
A vowel with modulated pitch frequency	Several first harmonics are coupled	Several first harmonics are coupled	Areas of the second and third formants are coupled with the entire spectrum

The results obtained prove the presence in the vocalized speech signal of the component-to-component phase couplings, which can be established by means of bispectral analysis. Revealing of these couplings seems to be possible provided the parameters of the speech production model are time invariant during the time period of the analysis.

Fig. 1. The bispectral analysis main program flowchart

Puc. 2. The bispectral analysis algorithm flowchart

Fig. 3. The results of the bispectral analysis of the vowel 'e' male speaker without pitch modulation
 a, b – bispectrum and biphase of prediction error; c, d – bispectrum and biphase of spectral envelope vowel 'e'

Fig. 4. The results of the bispectral analysis of the vowel 'e' male speaker with pitch modulation
 a, b – bispectrum and biphase of prediction error

Fig. 5. The results of the bispectral analysis of the vowel 'e' female speaker
 a, b – bispectrum and biphase of prediction error for signal without pitch modulation;
 c, d – bispectrum and biphase of prediction error for signal with pitch modulation

Conclusions. Application of state-of-the-art computer-aided bispectrum analysis tools has been proved very efficient to study component-to-component phase couplings between harmonics of speech signals with pitch and overtones. There is a dialogue program tool for bispectrum analysis of speech signals. Parametric description of the speech signal based on liner prediction was used to reveal the nature of component-to-component phase coupling of the speech components. In case of fixed states of the vocal tract (unchangeable vowel) and fixed pitch frequency the phase coupling can be found between separate harmonics of the original speech signal and excitation signal. Bispectral analysis of the frequency response of the synthesis filter shows that formant areas are coupled. The coupling remains in presence of the pitch modulations. The methods and tools of the component-to-component signal processing are applicable not only for speech processing, but also for other kinds of super broadband and polyharmonic signals.

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